

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Ludwigia species — most prevalent broad-leaved weeds in wet zone ricefields of Sri Lanka

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We surveyed ricefield weeds in four major rice-growing districts in the wet zone (western and southern provinces) of Sri Lanka 1984-85. Villages were sampled according to a probability proportionate to the area under cultivation in each district, based on Department of Census and Statistics data. Two ricefields per village, 1 km apart, were taken randomly. The ricefields surveyed were regarded as reasonably representative of rice-growing conditions in each district.

Both narrow-leaved and broad-leaved species were counted in each field and frequency of occurrence determined for all major weed species. Level of infestation of each major weed was assessed on the basis of visual estimation of weed cover.

Isachne globosa (Thunb.) Kuntze, *Fimbristylis miliacea* (L.) Vahl, *Cyperus iria* L., *Ischaemum rugosum* Salisb., *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., and *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link were the dominant narrow-leaved weeds at all four sites (see table).

Two species of *Ludwigia* appeared to be the most prevalent broad-leaved weeds. *Ludwigia hyssopifolia* (G. Don) Exell was the most frequent broad-leaved species, with moderate to heavy infestations in most fields surveyed. In addition to being found within the field or on bunds, the species also grew luxuriantly along the numerous minor waterways, streams, and irrigation canals.

Ludwigia decurrens Walt. was recorded for the first time in Sri Lanka. A relatively recent introduction to the island, it is spreading rapidly in the wet zone. It was well-established in Kalutara

Occurrence and levels^a of infestation of *Ludwigia hyssopifolia* and *L. decurrens* in 4 ricegrowing districts in the wet zone of Sri Lanka, 1984-85.

District	Fields (no.) sampled	Fields (no.) with given level of infestations ^b					Frequency of occurrence (%)
		0	1	2	3	4	
<i>L. hyssopifolia</i>							
Gampaha	176	9	14	93	57	3	94.8
Colombo	80	4	21	26	20	9	95.0
Kalutara	168	4	48	77	36	3	97.6
Galle	234	14	63	121	32	4	94.0
<i>L. decurrens</i>							
Gampaha	176	158	10	8	—	—	11.4
Colombo	80	14	4	31	22	9	82.5
Kalutara	168	18	40	61	47	2	89.3
Galle	234	226	—	4	2	2	3.5

^a 0 = weed species not observed, 1 = a few plants, 2 = occasional patches (weed cover 10-25% of area assessed), 3 = weed widespread throughout field (weed cover 26-50% of area assessed), 4 = dense and severe infestation (weed cover 51-75% of area assessed), and 5 = weed dominant, masking crop (weed cover 76-100%). ^b Neither weed attained 76-100% coverage.

and Colombo districts, with moderate to heavy infestations in most fields surveyed. In 1985, it occurred in only 10% of the fields surveyed in Gampaha district and 3.5% of those in Galle district.

Farmer interviews revealed that both

species are troublesome. Their extensive root system and rapid growth rate may lead to the removal of large amounts of nutrients added to rice. Currently, control is by hand-pulling, particularly of larger plants. □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Striga densiflora Benth., an angiospermic root parasite of rice in Bangladesh

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Striga densiflora Benth., a member of the Scrophulariaceae, has been reported as a noxious root parasite causing extensive damage to sugarcane crops in northern Bangladesh. In the 1986 dry season, we observed *Striga* parasitizing rice plants from Harian (Rajshahi) and from Rajbari. In 1987, in adjacent regions of Ishurdi, we found a number

Table 1. Damage caused by *Striga* in sugarcane and ricefields of Ishurdi, Bangladesh, 1987.

	Sugarcane	Rice
Fields surveyed (no.)	38	24
Fields infested (no.)	33	18
Fields totally damaged (no.)	10	4
<i>Striga</i> parasite (no./m ²)	84	37
Host plants (no./m ²)	5	221

of ricefields heavily infested with this angiospermic root parasite, with extensive damage to the premonsoon broadcast (Aus) rice crop (Table 1).

Infested plants were severely stunted with smaller leaves (Table 2). They failed to produce flag leaves; heavy infestations killed the rice plants. In

Table 2. Agronomic characters of rice plants from *Striga* infested and noninfested fields (n = 24). Ishurdi, Bangladesh, 1987.

Character	Noninfested	Infested	t-value ^a
Plant ht (cm)	82.57	46.52	10.60***
Fresh plant wt (g)	7.92	3.71	2.86**
Leaf length (cm)	36.11	24.32	10.57***
Internodes (no./plant)	3.08	2.00	5.56***
Internode length (cm)	8.64	3.14	6.39***
Stage of development	Maturing Panicle	No flag leaf	-

^a Significant at 0.1% (***) and 1% (**) levels.

mid-July, the parasite populations consisted of plants with mature fruits that were disseminating seed as well as plants in early and late juvenile stages of growth. The minute seeds of the parasite possess prolonged dormancy and can germinate across a very long period, making control by physical and chemical means difficult.

When a sugarcane crop is destroyed by the parasite, farmers usually grow rice in the *Striga*-infested fields, enabling the parasite to establish and parasitize rice as well. Because rice is much more widely cultivated than sugarcane, the

parasite is getting a choice of two hosts and there is a greater chance of it spreading to other areas of the country. Nongraminaceous crops, especially legumes and jute, are recommended for infested fields to avoid crop loss and parasite dissemination during the dry season. □

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Soil and Crop Management

Efficiency of urea supergranule (USG) under water stress at different growth stages

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Rice crops in most farming situations of northwest India are subjected to moisture stress during some growth stages, depending on rainfall and

Effect on yield of USG under water stress at different growth stages.^a Pantnagar, India, 1984-85.

Growth stage stress ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	Jaya, 1984		Pant Dhan 4, 1985	
	USG	Urea	USG	Urea
Early tillering (0-15 DT)	-	-	-	-
Active tillering (16-30 DT)	-	-	-	-
Advanced tillering (31-45 DT)	-	-	-	-
Near panicle initiation (46-60 DT)	-	-	-	-
Panicle initiation to flowering (61-90 DT)	-	-	-	-
Stress	6.0	5.7	4.7	4.1
- Stress	5.9	5.5	5.2	4.9
- - Stress	6.0	5.3	4.8	4.6
- - - Stress	5.9	5.6	5.2	4.8
- - - - Stress	6.2	5.6	NT	NT
Stress Stress	5.5	4.5	4.6	4.4
- Stress Stress	NT	NT	4.7	4.4
- - Stress Stress	5.6	5.6	4.8	4.9
- - - Stress Stress	5.4	4.9	4.9	4.5
Rainfed throughout crop period				
		LSD 5%	LSD 5%	
N carrier		0.3	0.2	
Water stress		0.6	0.4	
Interaction		ns	ns	
CV (%)		9.7	6.5	
Seeding date		12 Jun	1 Jun	
Transplanting date		17 Jul	11 Jul	

^a DT = days after transplanting, NT = not tried. ^b - = no water stress, stress = saturation during rains and about 20% depletion of available moisture during rainless periods.

and 2,033 mm in 1985. Rainfall distribution and pan evaporation are shown in the figure. The experiment was a split-plot design with four replications.

One month moisture stress during advanced tillering to panicle initiation resulted in a USG performance no better than that of urea (see table). In all other moisture stress treatments, including rainfed, USG was superior to urea. □

Weekly total rainfall and USWB pan evaporation (mm)

Weekly rainfall and USWB pan evaporation during the crop season. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1984-85.

irrigation. We compared efficiency of urea supergranules (USG) and urea effects on yield under varying periods of water stress at different growth stages in 1984-85 field trials. Soil was silt loam Aquic Hapludoll (pH 7.9, 1.8% organic matter, CEC 20 meq/100 g soil, 29% field capacity, and 10% permanent wilting point). Available soil water in the root zone was 100 mm. Total rainfall during the season was 1,377 mm in 1984